

The Participation of Black Ha Nhi People in Y Ty, Lao Cai Province For Local Sustainable Tourism Development

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SUMMARY

From the application of theoretical issues about the local community in sustainable tourism development, the article analyzes and evaluates the role, level and form of participation of the local community – Black Ha Nhi people Y Ty in local sustainable tourism development. The studies show that at the Y Ty destination, the Black Ha Nhi have actively participated in the development of tourism in the locality. It can be said that they are the people who laid the foundation, pioneered and are an indispensable core component for local tourism activities. However, due to many different reasons (the economic conditions of the local community are still difficult, the level of awareness, especially awareness of knowledge, experience, and skills in tourism, etc.) is still limited. Their participation in tourism activities has not been highly effective. From there, the article proposes some recommendations to promote strengths and take advantage of opportunities; to limit weaknesses and challenges to promote more effectively the role of the Black Ha Nhi in particular, the local community in general, in the sustainable development of tourism in Y Ty.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, sustainable tourism development is a matter of interest to many countries and ethnic groups because it not only brings great benefits in the present time but also preserves the benefits in the future and especially is to protect the natural environment and social culture.

In sustainable tourism development, local communities have a very important role. It helps to balance the pillars of the Economy - Environment - Society; contributing to creating great resources for tourism development. If we know how to appropriately manage and exploit science, we will promote local communities' role in sustainable tourism development. From the analysis and evaluation of the participation of local communities - Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty in local tourism development, the article proposes some solutions to improve the effectiveness of participation of local communities in Y Ty commune, Bat Xat district, Lao Cai province in the direction of sustainable tourism development. This article has 3 parts. Part 1 is about Some theoretical issues about local communities and sustainable tourism development; Part 2 is presenting the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in

tourism development in Y Ty and Part 3 is about Some recommendations.

RESULTS

I. Some theoretical issues about local communities and sustainable tourism development

1. Sustainable tourism development

1.1. Concept

1.1.1. Tourism

Tourism means activities related to people's trips outside their regular places of residence for a period of no more than 01 consecutive year to meet the needs of sightseeing, relaxation, entertainment, learning and discovery of natural resources tourism resources or in combination with other lawful purposes¹.

1.1.2. Sustainable tourism development

Sustainable tourism development is “the development of tourism that simultaneously meets socio-economic and environmental requirements, but besides that, it must harmonize the interests of the subjects participating in tourism activities, without harming the interests of tourists

¹ Vietnam Tourism Law - 2017, Chapter 1, Article 3, Section 1

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detrimental to the ability to meet future tourism demand”. In other words, sustainable development is developing and preserving for the future².

1.2. Tasks of sustainable tourism development

There are three main tasks: to ensure the harmonization of interests between the actors; develop and ensure harmony in economy, culture - society and environment; sustainable development and meet the needs of future generations.

1.3. Principles of sustainable tourism development

Ensuring sustainable economic development:

Ensuring the long-term stable economic growth and

development of tourism, positively contributing to the economic development of the country and the locality.

Ensure sustainability of resources and environment:

Exploiting and using tourism resources for development not only satisfies current needs but also ensures tourism development needs for generations. On the other hand, tourism activities also contribute to the embellishment of resources and environmental protection.

Ensuring social sustainability: Tourism development has specific contributions to social development, ensuring fairness in development.

*** Three core points in sustainable tourism development ³**

1.4. Parties involved in sustainable tourism development

Parties in sustainable tourism development, include government, local authorities, tourism businesses, tourists, local communities, and non-profit organizations. Each party has certain roles and responsibilities and has an organic relationship with each other in sustainable tourism

development. Tourism scholars have suggested that local communities are one of the parties that play an important role to help balance the social pillars and contribute to strengthening the close linkages between the stakeholders. The parties involved in sustainable tourism development can be mapped in the following diagram:

Picture 1: Parties in sustainable tourism development

Source: Pham Hong Long (2018), Lecture on sustainable tourism development

² Vietnam Tourism Law - 2017, Chapter 1, Article 3,Section14

³ Source: Responsible Tourism,

<https://www.slideshare.net/duanesrt/rt-trainer-guide-unit1vn160414>

2. Local communities

2.1. Concept

The local community is one of the parties involved in sustainable development. Those are the people who live around the tourist destination, who are influenced and impacted by tourism and also affect tourism activities in the destination.

These people may be directly or indirectly affected by tourism; have direct and indirect impacts on tourism activities; participate self-consciously or unconsciously in the process of tourism activities in the locality.

2.2. The Role of local communities in sustainable tourism development

- Local communities play an important role in balancing social pillars. Contributing to promotion and introduction; especially enhancing the image of the destination in the eyes of tourists; Being an important local human resource, contributing to the development of human resources for local tourism; An important force in the development of specific local tourism products and environmental protection; An important force in preserving and promoting local cultural values.

- The Vietnam Tourism Law - 2017 has affirmed the right to participate and enjoy the benefits of the community, including the local community in tourism development, as:

+ The residential community has the right to participate in and enjoy lawful benefits from tourism activities; take responsibility for protecting tourism resources and local cultural identity; maintain security, order, social safety and environmental protection.

+ The residential community is facilitated to invest in tourism development, restore and promote various forms of culture, folk art, and traditional handicrafts, and produce local goods for service. tourists, contributing to improving the material and spiritual life of local people⁴.

- In tourism communities, the participation of the local community is very important and basic. The Law on Tourism of Vietnam - 2017, stipulates the development of community tourism as follows:

+ Individuals and households where community tourism development are given incentives to provide accommodation and food services; guiding tourists to visit and experience culture and lifestyle in the community; producing goods, traditional crafts and other services for tourists.

+ Provincial-level People's Committees organize research, survey and select locations with potential for community tourism development; adopt policies to support the initial necessary equipment and foster knowledge, and skills to serve tourists for individuals and households in the

community involved in providing tourism services; support the promotion of community tourism products.

+ Commune-level People's Committees where community tourism development organizes propaganda, dissemination and awareness raising of the community; building the community's commitment to preserve cultural identity, protect the environment, and behave in a civilized manner towards tourists.

+ Organizations and individuals exploiting and developing community-based tourism are responsible for respecting the culture and lifestyle and sharing benefits from tourism activities with the community⁵.

2.3. Forms of local communities' Participation in sustainable tourism development

Local communities participate in the business of serving tourists at home and locally; introducing and promoting local heritage to tourists; exploiting heritage to serve tourists; supervising, inspecting and evaluating tourism activities in the locality; planning tourist spots and tours in the locality; protecting, restoring and maintain heritage...

2.4. The participation levels of local communities in the tourism industry

Following Sue Beeton (2006), Local communities can participate in tourism at 07 levels: formal participation; passive participation; participation in the survey; participation for the benefit; join function; interactive and voluntary participation. Functional participation, interactive participation and voluntary participation are effective and meaningful levels for sustainable tourism.

3. Overview of Y Ty commune and Black Ha Nhi ethnic community

3.1. Overview of Y Ty commune

Y Ty is a highland commune, bordering the Bat Xat district. The whole commune has a total of nearly 800 households living in 15 villages. The inhabitants are mainly Hmong, Dao, Giay, Ha Nhi and Kinh ethnic groups. Located on rocky mountains with an altitude of more than 2000 m, Y Ty has a cool year-round climate with high mountain ranges and large divisions. There are peaks up to 2,660m high (Nhu Cu San mountain) almost all year round covered with clouds. Y Ty has a primeval forest rich in vegetation, and a variety of rare and precious animals, and there are many species of plants and animals listed in the Red Book of Vietnam. In the forest, there are many big trees that a few people hug. Walking in the Y Ty old forest, sometimes we can see a large waterfall pouring down white foam mixed with floating clouds, sometimes swooping down to cover the valleys.

Recognizing the value of Y Ty's tourism resources in tourism development in particular, economic development, and socio-cultural development in general, the People's Committees of Bat Xat district and Y Ty commune pay

⁴ According to Vietnam Tourism Law-2017, Chapter 1, Article 6, Section 1,2

⁵ According to Vietnam Tourism Law - 2017, Chapter 3, Article 19, Section 1,2,3,4

special attention to enact many policies to create conditions for people to develop tourism; at the same time, creating conditions in terms of administrative procedures so that tourists can easily approach the Y Ty destination.

3.2. Black Ha Nhi ethnic community in Y Ty

Among the ethnic groups living in Y Ty, Ha Nhi people have the largest population, accounting for 60% of the population, they live near water sources to ensure water for daily life and irrigation. They have many customs and strange and unique festival systems. This ethnic group lives in Trinh Tuong houses made of land - this is a rather special type of house, which still retains the original wildness in the traditional architectural style, which is attracted many tourists. The house is usually rectangular in structure, with a main door and high ventilation archway, no windows, but very warm in winter and cool in summer. The wall of the house is made of very thick land, from 30-40cm. The roof is mainly thatched with wood.

Besides the Trinh Tuong house, the festival system of the Ha Nhi people is also a unique intangible cultural heritage that can be exploited to serve tourism development. In particular, the Old and Dry Festival of the Black Ha Nhi ethnic group is also ranked as a national intangible cultural heritage; The Ngai Thau Terrace - Y Ty is recognized as a nationally famous landscape.

Black Ha Nhi people live a gentle and peaceful life but are quite closed. In recent years, due to the awareness of the role of tourism in economic development and poverty reduction, people have also learned how to do tourism. They learn to be intimate, help, and meet the needs of tourists.

II. The participation of Black Ha Nhi people in tourism development in Y Ty

1. Describe the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune in local sustainable tourism development

1.1. The role of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty in sustainable tourism development

Local communities in Y Ty play an important role in the formation and development of local tourism. As mentioned in the previous section, tourism in Y Ty was formed after many years compared to Sa Pa and other localities in Lao Cai province. Therefore, it can be said that the tourism service industry here is still very young. It was born from the local people meeting the needs of some tourists when they came to visit and experience Y Ty. In the beginning, it was only accommodation and food services, giving directions, etc., according to the needs of tourists. Therefore, it can be said that the local people are the pioneers, laying the foundation for the tourism service industry in Y Ty. After that, along with the time and the increase in the number of visitors to Y Ty over the years, the supply chain of tourism services for tourists has gradually been formed, and tourism services have also been improved and improved as high as it is today.

One of the important conditions of a tourist destination is the type of tourism resources. Local communities in Y Ty,

including Black Ha Nhi people, are the owners of natural and creative resources, and local cultural resources.

The Black Ha Nhi communities in Y Ty live mainly by farming and animal husbandry. They rely on natural resources for their livelihood. Through generations, they are very aware of the role and importance of nature for the survival of ethnic groups. Therefore, along with exploiting nature to serve life, the Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty also protect nature in their ways with customary laws and conventions of the village and family. Especially the Ga Ma Do Ceremony (Sacred Forest Offering) ...

Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty possess an extremely abundant, unique and strange cultural treasure that can attract tourists. From the tangible cultural heritages such as houses (especially houses of Ha Nhi people), handicraft items, costumes, food (salted meat hanging in kitchen guard, Ha Nhi beer), local specialities (vegetables - tubers - fruits, mushrooms... picked in the forest, ethnic herbal medicines, etc.) to intangible cultural heritages, such as folk songs, folk dances (Ha Nhi drum dance, harvest dance, etc), languages, folklore, customs, festivals, fairs, etc...can all be exploited and developed to become unique products for tourists. In fact, over the years, it has been proved that the natural and cultural resources in Y Ty have been a strong attraction for domestic and international tourists. They are the basic that tourists come to this land. And the local community is one of the first and very important components in cooperation to promote and introduce; especially enhance the image of the destination in the eyes of tourists.

The Ha Nhi community in Y Ty is also one of the important local human resources, contributing to the development of human resources for local tourism. According to the opinion of the leader of the local Culture, Sports and Tourism Management Department, in 2019, it is estimated that there will be more than 100 Black Ha Nhi people, specializing in providing services to tourists in the fields of tourism, such as accommodation, dining, shopping, directions, guides. Out of 15 homestay households, 2/3 of the owners are Black Ha Nhi people. In the peak season, each household has up to 4-5 people serving visitors. Because there are not many restaurants in Y Ty, the fair of ethnic minorities only meets on Saturdays, so when travelling in Y Ty, tourists often follow a package service. For example, when staying at a certain homestay, tourists often book meals, accommodation, navigation, and buy local products, ...

Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty are also an important force in the development of specific local tourism products and environmental protection. As mentioned above, tourism in Y Ty is spontaneous. The organization and management of tourism activities, including tourism products, just stop at encouraging, supporting, helping, making statistics, reporting, maintaining security and order, creating favourable infrastructure and collecting taxes on services. The activities that orient the strategy to develop tourism products, the tourism planning is still vague, or the organization of events

to serve the development of tourism is not regular. Therefore, tourism activities in Y Ty as well as tourism products are mainly based on the local community and operate spontaneously according to the needs of tourists. If tourists have any needs, locals will find ways to meet those needs.

On the other hand, the biggest demand of tourists when coming to Y Ty is usually to admire the natural scenery (mountains, forests, clouds, waterfalls, caves...) and to visit, experience, and enjoy cultural heritages (going to the market, watching the buying and selling scene of local people; buying unique and strange local products; enjoying ethnic foods and drinks; participating in experiences at festivals, customs and habits of ethnic minorities (ploughing fields, transplanting rice, making brocade ...). Therefore, Black Ha Nhi people are the main force to create products to serve tourists.

Recently, several households that do homestay service, have been sent to train and study in neighbouring localities. Besides traditional products for tourists, people also do some other services to serve tourists. For example, making huts and shacks made of bamboo for visitors to drink coffee in the morning and evening, enjoy the scenery or build a hut for hunting clouds at high points of the commune to serve tourists or open more massage services: sauna, herbal bath, herbal foot bath, ...

The Ha Nhi people in the Y Ty commune are also an important force in preserving and promoting local cultural values. This ethnic group possesses an abundant and unique cultural treasure. Traditionally, this ethnic group has always had a sense of preserving and preserving this cultural capital. Today, when participating in tourism activities, realizing the benefits of tourism and the tourists' need to discover, enjoy and experience the culture, ethnic minorities are increasingly realizing the values of traditional cultural heritage. Since then, they have voluntarily protected this heritage, and exploited it for tourism, bringing in income for families to contribute to poverty reduction and economic development.

1.2. Forms of Participation of Black Ha Nhi People in sustainable tourism development

Through preliminary surveys and interviews with cultural managers in the area, the forms of participation in tourism development of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune are very abundant and effective. They have just started serving tourists at home and in the local area (Homestay, restaurants, selling souvenirs, ...), and cooperated with other local tourism service businesses to provide tourist services at the request of tourists (navigation, motorbike taxi, buying local specialities, providing food materials, ...); Especially, on crowded occasions, homestays are often introduced to tourists or cooperate to provide additional services to meet the needs of tourists.

In the process of doing business in tourism services, the Black Ha Nhi are directly involved in the process of exploiting heritage to serve tourists, especially the tangible and intangible cultural heritages. Turn these cultural heritages

into unique products to serve tourists. The process of the waterfall is often accompanied by the process of protecting, restoring and maintaining the heritage, making the heritage richer and more attractive to tourists.

Recognizing the role of information and product introduction to tourists, the Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty also participate in the process of introducing and promoting the local heritage to tourists. However, due to economic conditions and not fully understanding the techniques and methods of information and promotion, they have only participated in small and irregular promotional programs, only spontaneous without having long-term and effective promotion plans and strategies.

In recent years, when tourism in the Y Ty commune has strongly developed, the commune people's government and local tourism management inspect local tourism activities. Besides local authorities, tourism management agencies, and commune police, some local people also participate in coordination in monitoring, inspecting and evaluating tourism activities in the locality (Checking staying, patrolling to maintain security in border areas, detecting and denouncing acts of encroachment on the environment and illegal status by tourists or agencies in local...)

Due to the limited knowledge and skills in tourism, the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in the planning process of tourist attractions and tours in the locality is still limited. Mainly, they follow what experts and authorities ask, hand-in-hand instruction without creativity.

1.3. Levels of Participation of Black Ha Nhi People in sustainable tourism development

Research on the participation levels of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune in tourism development in the area according to 7 levels of Sue Beeton (2006). Besides, consult experts and managers of tourism activities show that the local community is fully expressed at the 7 levels mentioned above. However, the ratio at different levels is different, specifically:

At the level of Participating by form: about 10%, only expressed in some households/individuals who are not interested in tourism activities. They make a living in other occupations. They do tourism because following the movement, their house is in a convenient location to open services and see neighbours doing it, they also do it, not “bread and butter”. Serving tourists is not the main way of earning a living.

At the level of “Passive participation”: about 70%, tourism service businesses/individuals participate according to the request, instruct local authorities and local tourism management staff mechanical way, passively without opinion, without creativity. When there are complicated problems in their business premises, they often let the water float or rely on the support and help of various levels of government and mass organizations, rather than trying to find

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a way. solving problems. Therefore, many local tourism business establishments have not yet made a difference, highlighting in business strategies and methods among tourism service businesses. When there are difficult and complex problems in their business, they often rely on the support and help of the government, rather than trying to find a way to solve the problems. Therefore, quite a few local tourism businesses have not yet made a difference, highlighting business strategies and methods among tourism service businesses.

At the level of "Participating for the benefit": 100% of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty participate in local tourism development because of benefits and more than 90% benefits that people want is an economic benefit. Other benefits such as promotion, preservation of ethnic cultural identities, national pride, broadening understanding, and connecting with friends, ... are low percentages. The majority of local people participate in tourism development to increase their income, improve their economic situation, and even enrich themselves and their families.

At the level of "Functional participation": the majority of Ha Nhi Black Y Ty people participate in tourism activities usually in a general way without specializing assignment. For example, an accommodation business premises (homestay) can provide other general services such as dining, selling local specialities, giving directions, motorbike taxis, etc. (Bedroom: can be from the family's house, it is also possible to build more on the family's land, the bedroom attendants are descendants of the family, relatives, rarely hire outsiders; food services are sometimes available livestock and farming products of the family; local speciality products provided to tourists can also be made by family members, relatives, ...). This comes from the local economic, cultural and social, and also from the conditions of each family, if there are human resources that can provide these services, they are ready to provide them for the tourist. Therefore, tourism services here have no specialization,

activities are still spontaneous and without professional skills, often change over time and are unstable. However, when each homestay premises open, besides exploiting the family's resources, the family also mobilizes resources from outside when having many tourists and a scarcity of materials.

At the level of "Interactive participation" (the local community has the right and obligation to contribute ideas to the local tourism industry): It can be seen that this participation of the Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty is still faint, not effective. Because the residents living in Y Ty commune are mainly ethnic minorities, they do not have extensive knowledge (knowledge and skills) about tourism as well as tourism development. On the other hand, because they are quite new, they do not have much experience in the field of tourism. Therefore, they often passively make requests of local authorities and tourism managers and have little interaction in terms of policies, orientations and long-term strategies with the authorities for the development of the local tourism industry. Therefore, they do not get valid opinions when they are consulted.

At the level of Voluntary participation (Communities voluntarily participate in tourism even if it is not for their benefit): According to local tourism managers, ethnic communities in Y Ty participate in tourism activities are still heavy on economic benefits. Therefore, when participating in local tourism development activities without bringing immediate economic benefits, self-awareness is not high. Their awareness of the importance of tourism to their locality as well as their influence on sustainable tourism development is not deep.

Thus, it can be seen that the level of participation of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune in sustainable tourism development has many positive points, but there are still many limitations. Especially, at levels considered important for sustainable tourism development (functional participation, interactive participation and voluntary participation).

2. Evaluation of some contents in the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune in sustainable tourism development (according to SWOT)

2.1. Strengths, and weaknesses of the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune in local tourism development

Contents	Strengths	Weaknesses
* Forms of participation of Black Ha Nhi people in sustainable tourism development		
- Business services to serve tourists at the local family.	The services are quite diverse, and meet the basic needs of tourists.	Small business, no specialization
- Cooperation in the tourism service business in the locality.	There has been support among tourism service business households in crowded times; or other business that is not popular locally.	Not often, the efficiency is not high, the cooperation relationship is not strong.
- Participate in the process of promoting the local heritage to tourists.	Recognizing the value of local natural and cultural heritage in tourism development; Participating in the promotion process if required; mainly promoting in a small way,	Lack of initiative, positivity and creativity; also participate on request; not bold, lacking and weak in information technology and technology knowledge in advertising.

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	posting photos and videos on social networks such as Facebook and fan page, zalo, ...	
- Participate in the process of heritage exploitation for tourists	Enthusiastic and responsible in heritage exploitation; there are some unique ideas, that attract tourists to heritage mining.	Not having enough experience, knowledge and necessary skills in exploiting heritage for tourism; Sometimes improper exploitation leads to the risk of deforming the heritage.
- Participate in monitoring, inspection and evaluation of tourism activities in the locality.	Participating when requested; following the assignment of tasks.	Not properly aware of their roles and responsibilities in inspecting, monitoring and evaluating tourism activities; participation is not very effective.
- Participating in the process of planning tourism destinations and tours in the locality.	Enthusiastic; Follow the assignment of tasks.	Not having enough knowledge, experience and skills in business and planning tourist destinations and tours; the participation is not very effective
- Participating in the protection and restoration of heritage...	Conscious of the value of heritage, active and self-disciplined in performing assigned tasks.	Not knowing how to protect and restore the heritage; the efficiency is not high
* Levels of participation of Black Ha Nhi people in tourism development		
Participating by form	Forming a movement, encouraging everyone to participate in tourism development activities in the locality.	Superficial, don't care enough, not thinking, looking for creative and effective ways.
Passive participation	Participating in the assignment and guidance of local authorities and tourism managers	Perform machinery, no creative ideas.
Participating in the benefit	Having a high rate, especially focusing on economic benefits, immediate benefits	Long-term benefits, and other benefits economics have not been noticed.
Functional participation	Effective in families, clans, on a small scale	Not strict and regular for the village community; specialization is not high.
Interactive participation	Specific, direct, small-scale activities	Long-term strategic activities, large-scale activities
Voluntary participation	Actively, self-consciously with activities that directly benefit individuals and families	Lack of self-discipline and enthusiasm in activities that do not bring direct and immediate benefits to individuals, families and communities.

2.2. Opportunities and threats for the participation of Black Ha Nhi people in sustainable tourism development in Y Ty commune, Bat Xat, Lao Cai

Contents	Opportunities	Threats
- Business services to serve tourists at home and in the locality.	- Visitors coming to Y Ty are increasing day by day, the next year is higher than the previous year; - Local and central governments create favourable conditions in terms of mechanisms, policies and infrastructure for the local community to develop tourism business.	- The local community's knowledge and skills in the tourism service business are still lacking and weak. - The resources of the locality, as well as the tourism service business households, are limited. Most households have average below-average economic potential, so investment in business development is difficult.
- Cooperation in the tourism service business in the locality.	- Local authorities issue policies to encourage cooperation between households and develop tourism businesses.	- The lack of understanding of some Black Ha Nhi people in Y Ty commune about tourism business as well as the mechanism of tourism business cooperation with outside businesses

	- Enterprises outside the locality with good economic potential already were and are looking for ways to cooperate with the locality to invest in the tourism business.	- The difference in knowledge and business between Black Ha Nhi people and businesses.
- Participate in the process of introducing and promoting local heritage to tourists.	- The Internet and wifi network have covered the centre of Y Ty commune, which is convenient for promoting information about tourism services; - Smartphones have become a popular means of communication for tourists. - The State has organized many events in Y Ty, helping to promote Y Ty's image	- Weakness in awareness, use and management of modern technical and technological means to promote, propagate, and introduce natural heritages, and cultural and local tourism services. - The economic potential of the ethnic minority community in Y Ty is not strong enough to invest in advertising on the Internet.
- Participate in the process of heritage exploitation for tourists.	- The authorities of Lao Cai province have been giving guidelines, policies, and regulations, ... to encourage, support and invest in Black Ha Nhi people to participate in the exploitation of heritages, serve tourists and supervise, inspect and evaluate tourism activities as well as participate in the process of planning tourist attractions and tours; Protect, restore and maintain local heritage.	Perception of Black Ha Nhi people on knowledge, skills and experience in exploiting local heritage for tourism development and monitoring, checking and evaluating tourism activities. Participating in the planning process planning tourist spots, and tours; Participating in the protection, restoration and maintenance of local heritage are weak. Even many people do not have enough knowledge to do this task.

III. Some recommendations

From the analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the participation of the local community in Y Ty commune in tourism development, the essay proposes the following recommendations:

1. For local authorities and tourism businesses in Y Ty commune

- Helping the local community in general, Black Ha Nhi people in particular, improve by participating in the tourism business process by paying more attention to sharing benefits with the local community in the serving tourism development process in Y Ty commune. When life is improved and enhanced by participating in tourism activities, people will be more aware of the value of tourism resources, thereby having a sense of protecting tourism resources in the locality, protecting the environment, and contributing to sustainable tourism development.

- Encourage the participation of local communities, including the Black Ha Nhi in tourism development activities by recognizing and highlighting the role of local people in sustainable tourism development in the locality; Use the local human resources to improve the quality of tourism products and enrich tourism resources and products; Thereby creating local resources in protecting local resources and environment.

- Regularly consult with the local community on tourism development to combine tourism development with other concerns of the local community. Using local skills, knowledge and resources to assess the feasibility of tourism development projects and measures for sustainable tourism development. At the same time, it also avoids the arising of

conflicts or even antagonisms about the interests of the local community with the investment organization.

- Organizing training and retraining courses to help local communities improve their knowledge and skills in the tourism business. At the same time, have the correct awareness of the value and necessity of protecting natural resources and the environment, policies, laws of the environment and tourism business.

- Orienting people to promote local natural and cultural heritage values to participate appropriately in sustainable tourism development: participate in providing goods and services for tourism businesses: goods are materials for restaurants, hotels, amusement parks, and transportation services, Participating in providing direct services to visitors: catering services, accommodation facilities; working at tourism companies and enterprises, hiring local workers, creating a binding connection between the community and the tourism industry,...

- Applying advanced technologies and techniques to protect the environment and recover from the decrease in resources that are directly related to tourism development activities.

2. For local communities in general and Ha Nhi people in particular in Y Ty commune

- It is necessary to continue to promote the core role in the development of tourism products in the locality; provide more services for tourists; tourism is one of the important means to contribute to poverty reduction, and improve material and spiritual life for themselves, their families and society.

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- It is necessary to continue to promote the core role in the development of tourism products in the locality; provide more services for tourists; tourism is one of the important means to contribute to poverty reduction, and improve material and spiritual life for themselves, their families and society.

- Actively contribute ideas and participate in tourism development activities in the locality; provide necessary human and material resources for local tourism businesses.

- Implement and educate children and grandchildren in a civilized lifestyle of tourism. Having a polite, friendly and hospitable attitude shown in welcoming and communicating with tourists.

- Educating children in a civilized way of life. Having a polite, friendly and hospitable attitude shown in welcoming and communicating with tourists.

- Raise the awareness of protecting tourism resources and the environment; preserve and promote traditional cultural identity in service of tourism; maintain security and social order, ensuring local security and safety for tourists.

- Participating responsibly and effectively in supervising the implementation of investment and development of tourism products of enterprises in the locality, following the regulation of law, guidelines and policies of the Party, State and local authorities.

- Actively self-study and self-research to improve qualifications in all fields, especially in the field of sustainable tourism, to actively contribute to exploiting local cultural heritages to develop tourism products.

CONCLUSION

Local communities play a particularly important role in tourism development. Over the years, local communities in general and Black Ha Nhi people in particular in Y Ty commune have played a pivotal role in local tourism development. However, the research results show that, at the important levels in assessing the sustainable development of tourism, the results are not high. The current development of tourism in Y Ty was and is potentially at risk of unsustainable development, which can lead to overcrowding of the destination and loss of cultural identity due to ignorance and exploitation of traditional heritage. And if the development continues like this, in the future, tourism in Y Ty will again step on the "tourist trail" of Sa Pa today.

In the development of sustainable tourism in Y Ty, it is necessary to have synchronous coordination of the parties: the Government, local authorities, tourism business enterprises, tourists, non-profit organizations and especially local communities. Participants must always promote their responsibilities, and build close organic cooperation relationships to overcome invisible barriers such as dispersion, fragmentation, locality, and jealousy in the locality. Local authorities and tourism businesses in Y Ty

need to create a trust for local communities, including Black Ha Nhi people, and need to wisely choose appropriate ways and measures to ensure Y Ty tourism can be successful, can develop sustainable tourism; associated with preserving and promoting the cultural identities of ethnic groups, to further concretize tasks, turn potentials into advantages, develop Y Ty tourism and become a spearhead economic sector, creating jobs, increase income, contribute to stabilizing social security in the locality./.

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